

**XINOLIN ALKOLOIDI BUXARAINGA NITROLOVCHI ARALASHMA
TA'SIRINI O'RGANISH**

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Xinolin alkaloidlari tabiiy va sintetik biologik faol birikmalar sinfi bo'lib, ular farmakologiya va tibbiyotda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu sinf vakillari antibakterial, antifungal, antiviral, antitumor, antikonvulsant va antituberkulyoz faolliklarni namoyon qilishi bilan tavsiflanadi [1–3]. Xususan, xinolin hosilalari *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans* hamda *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* kabi patogen mikroorganizmlarga nisbatan samarali ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniqlangan [2,4]. Xinolin alkaloidlarining biologik faolligini oshirish maqsadida ularning strukturaviy modifikatsiyasi keng qo'llaniladi. Shunday modifikatsiyalardan biri molekulaga nitro-guruh kiritish hisoblanadi. Nitro hosilalar ko'pincha boshlang'ich birikmalarga nisbatan yuqori antibakterial, antifungal va antituberkulyoz faollik namoyon qiladi [4,5]. Bu holat nitro-guruhning kuchli elektronakseptor xossasi, molekuladagi elektron zichlikni qayta taqsimlashi va biologik membranalardan o'tuvchanlikni oshirishi bilan izohlanadi [6]. Ko'plab tadqiqotlarda xinalin va furoxinalin alkaloidlarining nitrolanish reaksiyalari turli nitrolovchi sistemalar yordamida amalga oshirilgan. Jumladan, konsentrlangan nitrat va sulfat kislotalar aralashmasi, atsetil nitrat, nitroniy tetraftorborat va boshqa yumshoq nitrolovchi reagentlar qo'llanilgan [7,8]. Reaksiya natijasida asosan aromatik sistemaning elektron zichligi yuqori bo'lgan holatlarida mono- yoki dinitro hosilalar hosil bo'lishi kuzatiladi [8]. Furoxinolin alkaloidlari qatoriga mansub bo'lgan buxarain molekulasi tarkibida kondensirlangan aromatik sistema hamda elektron donor xususiyatga ega funksional guruhlar mavjudligi sababli elektrofil almashinish reaksiyalariga nisbatan yuqori reaktivlik namoyon qiladi [8].

Shu jihatdan buxarainning nitrolanish reaksiyasini o'rganish yangi biologik faol hosilalarni olish nuqtai nazaridan muhim hisoblanadi. Strukturaga nitro-guruh kiritilishi molekulaning elektron tuzilishini o'zgartirib, uning fizik-kimyoviy va farmakologik xossalariga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin [5,6].

Buxarainning nitrolanish reaksiyasi quyidagi sharoitlarda amalga oshirildi: 50 ml hajmli tubi yumaloq kolbaga 0,2 g buxarain va 5 ml sirka kislotasi solinib, aralashma bir jinsli holatga kelguncha aralashtirildi. So'ngra nitrolovchi aralashma - konsentrlangan nitrat va sulfat kislotalar aralashmasi ($\text{HNO}_3 : 3\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$) aralashtirib turilgan holda 1 soat 30 daqiqa davomida uch qismga bo'lib tomchilab qo'shildi. Reaksiya 50°C haroratda uzluksiz aralashtirish sharoitida olib borildi. Bunda substrat va nitrolovchi reagentlar miqdoriy nisbati 1 : 1,7 etib tanlandi. Reaksiya davomiyligi 11 soatni tashkil etib, uning borishi yupqa qatlamli xromatografiya (YuQX) usuli yordamida muntazam nazorat qilib borildi. Reaksiyada quyidagicha mahsulot chiqishi mumkinligi o'rganilmoqda:

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI (REFERENCES)

1. Shang X.F., Morris-Natschke S.L., Liu Y.Q., Guo X., Xu X.S., Goto M., Li J.C., Yang G.Z., Lee K.H. Biologically active quinoline and quinazoline alkaloids. // *Medicinal Research Reviews*. – 2018. – Vol. 38, № 3. – P. 775–828.
2. Guo Y., Xu T., Bao C., Zhang Y., Xin X., Wang Z. Design and synthesis of new norfloxacin-1,3,4-oxadiazole hybrids as antibacterial agents against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. // *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. – 2019. – Vol. 136. – Art. 104966.

3. Irfan M., Alam S., Manzoor N., Abid M. Effect of quinoline based 1,2,3-triazole and its structural analogues on growth and virulence attributes of *Candida albicans*. // *PLoS ONE*. – 2017. – Vol. 12, № 4. – e0175710.
4. Shruthi T.G., Subramanian S., Eswaran S. Design, synthesis and study of antibacterial and antitubercular activity of quinoline hydrazone hybrids. // *Heterocyclic Communications*. – 2020. – Vol. 26, № 1. – P. 137–147.
5. Verma V.A., et al. Biological evaluation and docking studies of quinoline derivatives against COVID-19 virus main protease. // *Journal of Molecular Structure*. – 2021. – Vol. 1229. – Art. 129829.
6. Bharadwaj S.S., et al. Design, synthesis and pharmacological studies of some new quinoline Schiff bases. // *New Journal of Chemistry*. – 2017. – Vol. 41. – P. 8568–8585.
7. Mahajan A., Chundawat T.S. Review on the role of the metal catalysts in the synthesis of pharmacologically important quinoline substrate. // *Current Organic Chemistry*. – 2019. – Vol. 23, № 13. – P. 1441–1460.
8. Morrell A., Placzek M., Parmley S., Grella B., Antony S., Pommier Y., Cushman M. Optimization of the indenoisoquinoline topoisomerase I inhibitors: systematic study of the substituents in the indenoisoquinoline ring system. // *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. – 2006. – Vol. 49, № 26. – P. 7740–7753.